

Large-area dynamic contrast MHz optical coherence tomography for label-free imaging of porcine tissue

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ABSTRACT

We demonstrate a 3.2 MHz-OCT system for inter-volumetric dynamic optical coherence tomography of *ex vivo* porcine kidney tissue. Employing a home-built Fourier Domain mode locking (FDML) laser with a 1310 nm wavelength, the system achieved a lateral resolution of 3.48 μm and a frame rate of 612 Hz. A motorized XYZ positioning stage enabled the precise acquisition of multiple volumes, which were seamlessly stitched together to generate a comprehensive dataset with a total area of $2.6 \times 2.6 \text{ mm}^2$. Validations against histological sections confirmed the system's ability to visualize cellular tissue structures.

Keywords: Optical Coherence Tomography, OCT, Megahertz OCT, Fourier Domain Mode Locking, FDML, Dynamic OCT, Functional OCT, Tissue Dynamics, Kidney, Three-dimensional image acquisition

1. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic optical coherence tomography (dOCT) represents a significant advancement in medical imaging, offering several benefits over conventional OCT. By enabling the visualization of tissue dynamics without using exogenous contrast agents, dOCT improves the differentiation between various tissue types and facilitates the detection of abnormalities with greater clarity. The technique captures changes in the OCT signal induced by dynamic tissue movements, such as blood flow or cellular motion, which subsequently affect the phase or intensity of the OCT signal. By acquiring a time series of B-scans over several seconds, dOCT allows these dynamic changes to be visualized and represented in color [1-4].

This work presents inter-volume dOCT imaging of *ex vivo* porcine kidney tissue utilizing a 3.2 MHz-OCT system. MHz imaging is crucial for capturing dynamic processes in real-time, as it allows for observing rapid changes in tissue properties with minimal motion artifacts. The 3.2 MHz-OCT system delivers the necessary temporal and spatial resolution to accurately monitor and visualize these rapid dynamics, providing a comprehensive and detailed assessment of tissue functionality and structure. In addition, a home-built motorized, controllable XYZ positioning stage extends the scanning range by moving the scan head of the OCT system. The precise control of the XYZ positioning stage enables high-resolution imaging over large areas without compromising image quality. The study outcomes are analyzed and compared with histological findings.

2. METHODS

The used OCT system was equipped with a home-built Fourier Domain mode locking (FDML) laser source with a center wavelength of 1310 nm and a 3.2 MHz A-scan rate. With a spectral bandwidth of about 100 nm, the OCT data were acquired with a sample depth of 12 bits and a sampling rate of 4 GSa/s (AlazarTech, ATS9373, Canada). The laser output was collimated (F260APC-C, Thorlabs Inc., USA) to a pair of galvanometer mirror scanners (dynAXIS 421, ScanLab GmbH, Germany) used in unidirectional scanning mode to acquire 3D volumes. The incident power on the sample was 11 mW. Imaging was performed using an objective with a 0.26 numerical aperture (M Plan Apo NIR 10X, Mitutoyo, Japan). A 4f optical system, comprising three spherical lenses (LA1399 C, LA1256 C, Thorlabs Inc., USA), was employed to achieve relay imaging of the galvanometer scan axis and to fill the microscope objective's back aperture. This configuration improved the objectives' illumination, ensuring fully utilized resolving power. Table 1 details the optical specifications and the imaging parameters of the applied volumetric scan-protocol described below.

Specifications	Values
$NA_{\text{Objective}}$	0.26
Power on sample	11 mW
Lateral resolution	3.48 μm
Subvolume size	2048 x 50 A-scans
Volume repetition number	50
Number of subvolumes	40
Frame rate	612 Hz
Volume rate	12.2 Hz
Volume duration	81.95 ms

Table 1 OCT imaging specifications for one subvolume

Fig. 1 Design of the positioning stage and 4f optical system

A home-built motorized XYZ positioning stage was employed to facilitate large-area mosaicking of the dOCT datasets. Using three linear axes, the positioning stage allows for precise and systematic scanning of extensive sample areas, covering approximately $20 \times 20 \times 20$ cm. Five stepper motors (QSH4218-51-10-049-10K, Analog Devices Inc., USA) and two triple-axis stepper motor driver boards (TMCM-3110-TMCL, Analog Devices Inc., USA) ensure accurate movement and alignment. The positioning stage offers a repeatability accuracy of less than one micrometer, enabling precise and consistent scan head positioning. Figure 1 illustrates the design of the XYZ positioning stage. A custom control software developed in LabVIEW (National Instruments, USA) synchronizes automated scan head positioning with the OCT imaging software.

With this setup, we scanned freshly explanted porcine kidney tissue obtained from a local butcher. The following imaging protocol was applied to all data. For dynamic volumetric contrast imaging, 40 subvolumes were recorded, each consisting of 2048 x 50 voxels stacked in y-direction. Each subvolume was recorded sequentially 50 times sequentially at a volume rate of 12.2 Hz to obtain dynamic contrast. Afterward, the absolute values of the OCT signal for each pixel were Fourier-transformed along the time dimension. The amplitude integrals were calculated in three frequency bands and color-coded to create an RGB image. In this study, blue represents slow motion frequencies (< 0.5 Hz), green medium motion frequencies (0.5 - 3 Hz), and red fast motion frequencies (3 - 6 Hz). An adaptive histogram equalization was applied to the images to improve the contrast. The acquired color-coded subvolumes were subsequently registered and combined to form a comprehensive dataset and reshaped to create a quadratic dimension. A single volume has a size of about 1.4×1.4 mm². For large-area dynamic imaging, the scan head was moved three times with an overlap of approximately 15 %. Each time, a complete volume was acquired using the previously described procedure. The volumes were merged into one large data set of about 2.6×2.6 mm², as shown in Fig. 2. To assess the features observable in the dOCT dataset, a histologic tissue section was prepared and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dOCT image of the *ex vivo* porcine kidney tissue is shown in Figures 2 and 3. The horizontal planes of the individual volumes at corresponding depths are displayed on the left side of Fig. 3, while the right side presents the composite, stitched scan. The white dotted line indicates an exemplary, stitched OCT B-scan. Figure 3 displays one individually scanned OCT dataset alongside the H&E-stained histological cross-section to provide a detailed morphologic reference for comparing and evaluating the dOCT outcomes. It is important to note that the scale bars in the dOCT data and the histological section are not directly comparable. This discrepancy arises because histological processing can introduce a shrinkage factor of approximately two. As the shrinkage is not uniform across the entire sample, adjusting the scale bar to account for this variation is challenging. Additionally, the histological section does not correspond precisely to the same location as the dOCT data. Nonetheless, it provides adequate information for identifying and assessing the structures.

Fig. 2 Large-area dynamic OCT dataset of porcine kidney tissue. In the upper left corner, four individual *en face* views at 40 µm depth, each with an approximate overlap of 15 %, are displayed. The right side shows the corresponding stitched dynamic OCT *en face* view, which integrates the individual scans into a unified dataset. The white dotted line illustrates the location of the stitched B-scan.

In the dOCT volume, round and elongated structures are visible and represented in green, corresponding to areas of high dynamic signal associated with moving particles. In contrast, the surrounding regions are color-coded in blue, indicating a low dynamic signal. The green structures are likely renal tubules, as indicated by histological examination. Although the tissue was removed from the living organism, it may exhibit residual fluid movement, which the dynamic contrast approach detects.

Fig. 3 Comparison of dOCT and histology of porcine kidney tissue. A) dOCT *en face* view of porcine kidney tissue. B) Cropped 3D volume representation. C) Corresponding H&E-stained histological section of the same tissue sample.

4. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This study demonstrates inter-volumetric dynamic imaging of *ex vivo* porcine kidney tissue with a 3.2 MHz-OCT system. The imaging results prove that despite its relatively low axial resolution of 16 μm in air, the functional imaging technology allows the identification of cellular structures in the MHz-OCT volumes. Utilizing an XYZ positioning stage, we captured images from various sample locations and integrated them into a comprehensive dataset. This approach facilitated large-area dynamic analysis and detailed characterization of tissue structures. The results were compared with histological outcomes.

Considering the high imaging speed of the MHz-OCT system, we aim to adapt the dOCT technique for integration with our 4D real-time video-rate OCT software and utilize it for future *in vivo* applications. This advancement would greatly enhance the dynamic observation of tissue processes and interactions. Moreover, *in vivo* applications will facilitate the study of tissue structures and their dynamic changes within a living organism, providing valuable insights into physiological and pathological conditions.

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